

INDIA-EGYPT RELATIONS: A NEW ERA AFTER 2014

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Abstract:

India and Egypt are the founding members of the Non-Aligned Movement. Egypt, the most populous nation in West Asia, is a major player in the region. Egypt has tremendous value due to its strategic position at the intersection of Africa, Asia, and Europe. Due to its robust trading ties and free trade agreements with nations all over the African region, Egypt is also seen as a gateway to Africa. In every period, bilateral relations have undergone significant changes. With frequent interactions at the leadership and ministerial levels, the two nations' political collaboration increased in 2015. President Abdel Fattah al-Sisi and Prime Minister Narendra Modi met in September 2015 in New York during the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) meeting. The Egyptian President visited India in September 2016 and participated in the third India Africa Forum Summit in October 2015. Five Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) addressing public broadcasting, cyber security, cooperation on youth issues, and information and technology (IT) were subsequently signed between the two countries. They decided to initiate new engagements to intensify social military training and exercise. Around 3.15 billion dollars have been invested by more than 50 Indian businesses in various Egyptian economic sectors, including chemicals, energy, textile, clothing, agribusiness, and retail. The current president of Egypt has attended India's 74th Republic Day celebrations as a "Guest of Honor". During this meeting in New Delhi, Minister Narendra Modi, and Egyptian President El-Sisi decided to increase bilateral commerce to \$12 billion over the following five years. The president of Egypt's visit highlights Cairo's expanding significance for New Delhi. The primary objective of this research paper is to examine potential areas of cooperation between India and Egypt under the Narendra Modi Government. This paper also highlights the challenges faced by both countries regarding bilateral relations.

Keyword: Relationship, Visit, Cooperation, Significance, Challenges

Introduction

India and Egypt, two of the oldest civilizations, have maintained a history of close interaction since ancient times. Ashoka's edicts pertain to his interactions with Egypt during the reign of Ptolemy II. In contemporary history, Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi and Saad Zaghloul pursued analogous objectives about their nations' independence, culminating in a profound camaraderie between Gamal Abdel Nasser and Jawaharlal Nehru, which resulted in a Friendship Treaty between their countries in 1955. The inaugural Cultural Agreement between the two nations was inked in 1958, which anticipated the establishment of cultural centers within each other's territories. The establishment of the Maulana Azad Centre for Indian Culture (MACIC) as a cultural division of the Embassy of India in Cairo has provided an institutional manifestation of cultural interchange. Two significant factors were evaluated for establishing an Indian Cultural Centre in Egypt: 1- Cairo's substantial role as an intellectual and cultural hub of the Arab World and Africa. 2- Extensive and profound historical exchange of culture between the two civilizations. MACIC was established on 14th January 1992 and is named in honor of Maulana Abul Kalam Azad (1888-1958), a prominent scholar, educator, and statesman, who served as India's first Education Minister and was the founding President of the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (Indian Council for Cultural Relations [ICCR], 2024).

The connections between the populations of the two nations were founded on shared anti-British endeavors and mutual experiences in their nationalist quest for independence. This resulted in the simultaneous emergence of nationalist movements in both nations. In Egypt, Saad Zaghlul Pasha, via the Wafd party, advocated for independence, while in India, Mahatma Gandhi, Jawaharlal Nehru, Maulana Azad, and numerous others, through the Indian National Congress, strengthened the campaign for freedom. The two parties and their leadership sustained ongoing communication with one another. Nehru, who was deeply invested in India's foreign relations, sought to connect the Indian independence movement to a broader anti-colonial battle. He attended the International Congress against Imperialism in Brussels in February 1927. During the interwar period, Nehru visited Egypt multiple times, maintained strong connections with the leaders of the Wafd Party, and invited them to participate in the yearly sessions of the Indian National Congress. (Pasha, 2008) In a meeting with the visiting Egyptian Wafd delegation in India, Nehru stated: "Our peoples have shared significant

interactions since the dawn of history, exchanging ideas, cultures, and goods even in ancient times, and subsequently, in the modern era, engaging in a collective struggle for freedom against shared imperialism (Pasha, 2008, p. 140).”

Egypt and India have maintained a strong friendship based on their mutual resistance to foreign imperialism in the 1950s and 1960s. The robust alliances were illustrated by the establishment of the Non-Aligned Movement, initiated by Egypt’s President Gamal Abdel Nasser in conjunction with Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, Ghana’s Kwame Nkrumah, Sukarno of Indonesia, and Tito of Yugoslavia, intended to mitigate the ideological discord between East and West. Contemporary Egyptian-Indian relations trace their origins to the interactions between Saad Zaghloul, the Egyptian leader, and Gandhi of India, concerning their mutual objectives in their liberation struggles. In 1955, Egypt and India were founding members of the Non-Aligned Movement. In 1977, India characterized President El-Sadat’s journey to Jerusalem as a ‘courageous’ action and endorsed the peace accord between Egypt and Israel (El-Kamel, 2010).

In 1956, a test of friendship occurred when Britain and France launched an assault to reclaim control of the Suez Canal and overthrow the Nasser administration. India endorsed Egypt’s assertion and denounced the assault. Expressions of various G77 coalitions and South-South cooperation have been crucial in establishing a cohesive position on global matters for both nations (Srishti, 2023). Relations deteriorated during Hosni Mubarak’s leadership in Egypt (1981-2011). Mubarak was reportedly dissatisfied with India owing to a perceived diplomatic slight. Furthermore, India initiated the execution of a “Look East” policy. Egypt-India relations grew and gained direction only after Mubarak’s departure (Ramachandran, 2023). It is possible that this period, which lasted until the 1980s, is considered to be the zenith of relations between India and Egypt. In the decades since then, the two states’ regional and internal goals have become increasingly distinct. It is possible to argue that the COVID-19 pandemic and its global repercussions were the catalyst for the revitalization of numerous bilateral relationships. This is because the concept of “vaccine diplomacy” fostered tribalism within the international framework, with Western nations frequently monopolizing medical supplies while countries in the Global South lagged in vaccine equity. During the height of India’s Delta wave in 2021, Egypt was one of the countries that supplied oxygen for medicinal purposes (Taneja,

2022). Prime Minister Narendra Modi's visit to Egypt is a pivotal milestone in bilateral relations, being the first visit by an Indian Prime Minister since 1997 (Mohammed Soliman, 2023). There have been four Prime Ministerial visits to Egypt from India since the 1980s. These trips were made by Rajiv Gandhi in 1985, P. V. Narasimha Rao in 1995, I. K. Gujral in 1997, and Dr. Manmohan Singh in 2009, during the NAM Summit. In 1982, Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak made formal visits to India. In 1983, he attended the NAM Summit, and in 2008, he returned to India for another visit. Following the Egyptian Revolution of 2011, significant diplomatic exchanges continued to take place with Egypt, culminating in President Mohamed Morsi's visit to India in March 2013. In March 2012, the Minister of External Affairs traveled to Cairo, while in December 2013, the Egyptian Minister of Foreign Affairs traveled to India (Ministry of External Affairs, 2023).

India and Egypt Since 2014

In 2014, the NDA achieved electoral success and formed a government under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi. Since 2014, India has adopted a unique foreign policy strategy to promote national interests. India strengthened its bilateral relations with Egypt by engaging in various social, political, and economic domains. This interaction enhanced mutual understanding and collaboration across bilateral, regional, and international venues.

Political Ties

A rising convergence between India and Egypt on several global issues is occurring, as was indicated earlier, except for terrorism and the issue of economic cooperation. Both are nations that are part of the Global South. In December 2022, when India took over the presidency of the G20, it extended an invitation to Egypt, along with representatives from some other countries, to take part in the meetings as Visitors. The reform of multilateral institutions, sustainable development objectives, climate change, energy security, food security, and other issues are among the most important concerns that Cairo has taken seriously and indicated its interest in cooperating with India. Cairo has also expressed its desire to collaborate with India on these key topics. There were several Egyptian ministers present at the G20 summit that was held in India while India was holding the presidency of the group. To further enhance bilateral relations, reaching a consensus on these important global issues is highly

beneficial. In addition, India and Egypt have views that are comparable about the problem of climate change. Egypt is concerned about the severe droughts, spreading desertification, and rising sea levels that are occurring in the Mediterranean region because of climate change. Egypt is also an important player in the process of bringing together African nations to discuss the subject of climate change. When it comes to the topic of climate change, India and Egypt are both engaging in significant projects and bringing the voices of the Global South to the forefront (Pradhan, 2023).

High-Level Visits

Under the current leadership of Prime Minister Modi and President Sisi, it appears that India and Egypt have discovered common bilateral and regional concerns on which they can work together at a cooperative level. Cooperation with Egypt has been regarded as strategically vital due to the historical and civilizational tie between the two countries, as well as the rapidly shifting political and security scenario that both India and Egypt are currently confronting in their respective surroundings. While Sisi has been in power, he has shown interest in and taken steps to develop the relationship with India. Since he took office, he has traveled to India on three separate occasions for official reasons. In October of 2015, President Sisi traveled to India to take part in the participation in the third India–Africa Forum Summit. His second trip to India was an official one, and it took place in September 2016. In his conversation with Prime Minister Narendra Modi, he covered a wide range of topics, including the defense and security challenges that exist between the two nations. Additionally, he traveled to India in January 2023 to take part in the ceremonies of India’s Republic Day and to engage in extensive conversations with Prime Minister Modi throughout his trip. The fact that an Egyptian military unit took part in India’s Republic Day parade for the very first time is a sign that the two countries are becoming increasingly cooperative in terms of defense. The travels of President Sisi have unquestionably contributed to the consolidation of bilateral relations between India and Egypt in a variety of spheres (Pradhan, 2023).

In terms of bilateral relations, the visit that Prime Minister Narendra Modi made to Egypt from June 24 to June 25 is being regarded as a significant turning point. It has been said by the Egyptian ambassador Wael Mohamed Awad Hamed that it is anticipated that the two parties would agree to increase their level of cooperation in a variety of areas, including security, trade, and investment. Additionally, Egypt will offer

India a special slot within the Suez Canal Economic Zone, which will be discussed between the two parties. This will be in addition to the co-production of military equipment.

High-Level Visit between India and Egypt

Sr. No.	Official	Designation	Visiting Country	Year
1.	Shri Narendra Modi	Prime Minister of India	Egypt	2015
2.	HH Abdel Fateh Al Sisi	President of Egypt	India	2016
3.	Ms. Sushma Swaraj	External Affairs Minister of India	Egypt	2017
4.	HH Abdel Fateh Al Sisi	President of Egypt	India	2018
5.	Shri Narendra Modi	Prime Minister of India	Egypt	2019
6.	HH Sameh Shoukry	Foreign Minister of Egypt	India	2020
7.	Shri Narendra Modi	Prime Minister of India	Egypt	2021
8.	Shri Raj Nath Singh	Defence minister of India	Egypt	2022
9.	Shri Narendra Modi	Prime Minister of India	Egypt	2023

Sources: Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India.

The invitation that the President of Egypt received from the Prime Minister of India to be the chief guest for Republic Day in 2022 was extremely gracious and is considered to be this turning point in the strengthening bi-lateral relations between these two countries. In the 2010s, both Prime Minister Modi and President Sisi took office in their respective posts. The two leaders have the same aims, which include the modernization of their respective countries, the industrialization of their economies, the creation of jobs, expansion, and awareness of environmental issues. There is a connection between each of these concerns and the challenges that the developing world is currently facing. They have finally come together after a long period, and they can face issues together and put it in a bilateral context. Additionally, they can do so from the perspective of the G20, as Egypt has been invited as a guest country when India oversees the G20 presidency (Laskar, 2023).

Security and Defence Cooperation

When it comes to connection, defense collaboration is of utmost importance, and it is predicated on the level of comfort. It is not difficult to see the connection that exists between Egypt and India. There is a

strong connection between India's security of the Indian Ocean and the security of the Red Sea. For Egypt, the safety of the Suez Canal, which is a major conduit for international trade, is a component of the safety of the Red Sea and, as a result, is influenced by the safety of the Indian Ocean. They are both intricately connected to one another (Laskar, 2023). The cooperation between India and Egypt in the areas of defense and security is among the oldest in Arab countries. As early as the 1950s, both nations began working together to strengthen their defense capabilities. The defense and security cooperation between the two countries has not been successful as a result of the shifting geopolitical landscape in the region as well as the current condition of ties between the two countries. Both countries have reached an agreement to further expand the extent and content of their relationship when it comes to defense and security cooperation, which has emerged as significant areas of collaboration between the two countries. (Pradhan, 2023)

The speed and scope of the cooperation between the two nations have the potential to bring back the golden era of the relationship between India and Egypt, which was characterized by the leadership of Nehru and Nasser. The defense and security cooperation between India and Egypt has garnered fresh emphasis under the leadership of Prime Minister Narendra Modi and President Abdel Fattah El Sisi. At the ministerial and official levels, there has been a continuous exchange of visits that have been centered on matters about military and security. The Egyptian government has indicated that it is interested in purchasing planes and missiles manufactured in India. A defense cooperation agreement was signed between the two countries in 2022, during the visit of India's Defense Minister Rajnath Singh to Cairo. The threat of terrorism is something that both nations are concerned about, and they have reached an agreement to work together to combat it. In January of 2023, Abdul Fateh Al Sisi traveled to India to take part in the ceremonies of India's Republic Day. During this time, he engaged in extensive conversations with Prime Minister Modi. The fact that an Egyptian military unit took part in India's Republic Day parade for the very first time is a sign that the two countries are becoming increasingly cooperative in terms of defense. The travels of President Sisi have unquestionably contributed to the consolidation of bilateral relations between India and Egypt in a variety of spheres (Pradhan, 2023).

Egypt and India have friendly defense relations with one another. Egypt has been visited by many defense delegations (including aircraft and

naval ship transits) since June 2021, following a temporary pause that was caused by the COVID-19 epidemic. The visit of the Chief of Air Staff, Air Chief Marshal VR Chaudhari, to Egypt in November 2021 was followed by the visit of an Egyptian delegation led by the Commander of the Air Force, Air Marshal Abbas Helmy, in July 2022. This visit was a manifestation of the reciprocal relationship between the two countries. Activities carried out by the Joint Defense Committee (JDC) are responsible for determining most of the existing defense cooperation. Beginning in 2006, nine JDC meetings have been held in either country, with each conference being followed by activities that involve the exchange of information. In November 2019, the ninth meeting of the JDC was conducted in Cairo. From the 29th of July to the 2nd of August 2024, the 10th JDC was held in New Delhi (Embassy of India, 2024). In September 2022, Defense Minister Rajnath Singh traveled to Egypt, where he met with President Sisi and Defense Minister Mohamed Ahmed Zaki. During his tour, he engaged in a wide range of conversations regarding the defense cooperation that exists between the two nations. Additionally, a defense cooperation deal was struck between India and Egypt during this visit. This agreement intends to further strengthen the defense and security cooperation between India and Egypt, as well as to explore new areas of cooperation between the two countries. The Cairo West Airbase was another location that Rajnath Singh went to. The subsequent visit to Cairo in October 2022 was made by External Affairs Minister Subrahmanyam Jaishankar, which came after the visit made by Rajnath Singh. At the meeting, he met with his Egyptian counterpart Sameh Shoukry, and addressed several matters that are of mutual importance to both countries. Among the topics that were covered was the possibility of further enhancing the defense and security cooperation between the two nations. This kind of frequent high-level exchange of visits and discussions on matters of common concern has been a crucial contributor to the establishment of a strategic alliance between the two countries (Pradhan, 2023).

After a pause brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, bilateral mechanisms resumed their operations on March 3, 2021, with Videocon serving as the host of the Joint Working Group on Trade and Investment. The fifth meeting of the Joint Committee on Science and Technology took place in a virtual format on October 5, 2021. The topics that were discussed during this meeting were agriculture, nanotechnology, biotechnology, and renewable energy. Both the India-Egypt Workshops on Agriculture-Biotechnology and Nanotechnology took place in Shillong in September

2018, and Mumbai in January 2019, respectively. Both workshops focused on the technology of nanotechnology. From the 5th to the 7th of November 2019, Cairo played host to the 9th meeting of the JDC. An agreement was signed in June 2023, during the State Visit of Prime Minister Modi, which resulted in the upgrading of bilateral relations to the status of Strategic Partnership. Prime Minister Modi was also presented with the “Order of the Nile” during his visit to Egypt. This is the highest civilian award that can be given in Egypt. On May 3, 2023, the twelfth session of Secretary-level Foreign Office Consultations (FOC) between India and Egypt took place in Cairo. A discussion was held between both parties regarding the bilateral relations that exist between the two countries, as well as the necessity of enhancing cooperation in all areas, including the political, economic, defense, and cultural spheres. In addition to this, they discussed additional measures that may further improve cooperation in multilateral forums (Embassy of India, 2024).

In October of 2021, Cairo played host to the very first ever Joint Tactical Air Exercise between the Egyptian Air Force and the Israeli Air Force. For the very first time, a contingent from the Indian Air Force took part in the ‘Tactical Leadership Programme’ (TLP) that was held by the Egyptian Air Force during June and July 2022. The contingent consisted of three Su-30MKI aircraft and two C-17 aircraft. A joint exercise between the Egyptian Air Force and the Indian Air Force was carried out on May 8, 2023, at an Egyptian airbase. The purpose of the exercise was to help boost the military cooperation between the two countries. The multilateral tri-service exercise known as “Bright Star-2023,” which was led by the United States Central Command and the Egyptian Army and took place in August of 2023, was also attended by India for the very first time. The exercise known as “Cyclone-II” was carried out by the Special Forces in Egypt during January in the year 2024. From the 21st to the 26th of June 2024, Egypt played host to a bilateral Air Force Exercise that included four RAFALE aircraft from the Israeli Air Force (Embassy of India, 2024).

Trade and Economic Cooperation

Egypt is one of India’s most important economic partners on the African continent, and it has profited from investments by Indian companies totaling \$3.15 billion in the United States. Recently, during the fifth meeting of the India-Egypt Joint Trade Committee, which took place in

Cairo on July 25, 2022, India’s Ambassador to Egypt, Ajit Gupte, announced that India intends to inject around 700 million dollars’ worth of private investments in Egypt over the next several years. Over the past ten years, the amount of money moving back and forth between the two nations has increased by more than five times, reaching \$4.55 billion in the fiscal year 2018-19. The volume of trade decreased only a little, reaching US\$4.5 billion in FY 2019-20 and US\$4.15 billion in FY 2020-21, despite the COVID-19 epidemic. This number represents a slight decrease. In the fiscal year 2021-2022, exports and imports between the two nations reached a total of \$7.26 billion, representing a year-on-year increase of 75%. In the fiscal year 2022, India’s exports to Egypt were \$3.74 billion, representing a 65 percent rise over the previous year’s total. While this was going on, Egypt's exports to India over the same period reached \$3.52 billion, representing a rise of 86%. According to the information provided by the Egyptian Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), India has emerged as Egypt’s third-largest export market, sixth-largest trade partner, and seventh-largest exporter within the country of Egypt. After China, India was Egypt’s eighth-largest trading partner worldwide in the fiscal year 2021. Products such as mineral oil, petroleum, fertilizers, inorganic chemicals, cotton, and other such items make up the majority of India’s import basket from Egypt. In addition to cotton yarn, the most important products that India ships to Egypt are bovine meat, iron and steel, light automobiles, and cotton yarn (India Briefing, n.d.).

**India’s Trade Volume with Egypt
(2019-20 to 2023-24)**

(Values in US \$ Millions)

Year	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-24
EXPORT	2,504.23	2,264.37	3,743.92	4,109.41	3,520.62
% of Growth	-13.24	-9.58	65.34	9.76	-14.33
India’s Total Export	313,361.04	291,808.48	422,004.40	451,070.00	451,070.00
% of Growth		-6.88	44.62	6.89	-3.10
% of Share	0.80	0.78	0.89	0.91	0.81
IMPORT	2,031.38	1,892.40	3,520.83	1,951.54	1,157.44
% of Growth	21.07	-6.84	86.05	-44.57	-40.69

India's Total Import	474,709.28	394,435.88	613,052.05	715,968.90	678,214.77
% of Growth		-16.91	55.43	16.79	-5.27
% of Share	0.43	0.48	0.57	0.27	0.17
TOTAL TRADE	4,535.61	4,156.77	7,264.75	6,060.95	4,678.06
% Growth		-8.35	74.77	-16.57	-22.82
TRADE BALANCE	472.86	371.98	223.09	2,157.87	2,363.19

Sources: Data Bank, Ministry of Commerce, Government of India, accessed on 15.12.2024, <https://tradestat.commerce.gov.in/eidb/iecmt.asp>

The above table shows that over the past five years, India's trade performance has been marked by significant fluctuations. In 2019-2020, exports saw a decline of 13.24%, dropping to 2,504.23, and continued their downward trend in 2020-2021 with a decrease of 9.58%, reaching 2,264.37. However, exports rebounded strongly in 2021-2022 with a growth of 65.34%, reaching 3,743.92, and continued to rise by 9.76% in 2022-2023, hitting 4,109.41. In 2023-2024, exports saw a sharp decline of 14.33%, falling to 3,520.62. On the import side, imports increased by 21.07% in 2019-2020, reaching 2,031.38, but fell by 6.84% in 2020-2021 to 1,892.40. Imports surged dramatically by 86.05% in 2021-2022 to 3,520.83 but plummeted in the following years, falling by 44.57% in 2022-2023 and by 40.69% in 2023-2024, reaching 1,157.44. The total trade volume mirrored these trends, with a decrease of 8.35% in 2019-2020, followed by a sharp 22.82% drop in 2020-2021, but a remarkable 74.77% increase in 2021-2022. However, total trade declined again by 16.57% in 2022-2023 and by 22.82% in 2023-2024. Despite the fluctuations, India's trade balance showed a positive trend, with a surplus of 472.86 in 2019-2020, which dropped to 371.98 in 2020-2021 but saw a sharp improvement in 2022-2023, reaching 2,157.87, and further rising to 2,363.19 in 2023-2024. Overall, while exports and imports showed considerable volatility, the trade balance improved in recent years, driven by a decline in imports.

India intends to make use of the Suez Canal Economic Zone (SCZONE), which will in turn assist it in gaining access to markets in both Africa and Europe. India is the recipient of a specialized cluster in the industrial and logistics hub, which was recently announced by the authorities of SCZONE. This announcement offers a great deal of promise for further strengthening the economic relations that exist between the two

countries. Egypt intends to strengthen its commercial ties with India as well. Over fifty Indian companies are operating in Egypt, each of which is doing business in a different field. These companies are directly contributing to the expansion of the Egyptian economy and strengthening the bilateral connection (Pradhan, 2023).

Investment Cooperation

It has been reported by the Egyptian Ambassador in India that Egypt is currently in the process of signing three memorandums of understanding between the Egyptian government and the enterprises. These memorandums of understanding were taken by the nation and made into framework agreements. It is now legally obligatory on both sides, and there is a commitment on both sides that there will be investments from these three firms in Egypt, and this is something that is becoming increasingly important. In this moment, the nation looks at the amount of money that India has invested in Egypt, which is currently somewhere about \$3.5 billion. However, these three agreements will add twenty billion dollars to the total, which is a fair sum, something that Egypt values and something that Egypt believes will give us a satisfactory foundation. Therefore, it will expand by a factor of seven, and consequently, it will bring us to an entirely new level of collaboration. In the future, green hydrogen will be the fuel of choice. There is a very strong cooperation being developed between Egypt and India in the energy industry, and this partnership is going to bring about improved chances for our economic relationship (Laskar, 2023).

There have been roughly 55 Indian firms that have made investments in various industries in Egypt, with a combined investment that exceeds \$3.75 billion. These investments have provided employment opportunities for approximately 38,000 Egyptians, both directly and indirectly. In addition, some Indian corporations have made additional investments in the pipeline that total 700 million dollars in the United States. For the fiscal year 2023-24, Egypt has received investments from India totaling more than 170 million US dollars. Technology Mahindra, an Indian information technology company, launched its first global delivery center in Egypt in December 2022. Additionally, in March of 2023, Egypt inaugurated the first production line of “Hepatitis B and Pentavalent” vaccines, which had a capacity of 100 million doses yearly. This was accomplished in collaboration with the “Serum Institute of India” (SII). In April of 2024, Micromax began the production of feature

phones in Egypt under a ToT deal with KMG. The production will soon expand to include smartphones, wearables, and other electronic devices as well. Moreover, renewable energy companies Re-New, ACME, and OCIOR have signed memorandums of understanding (MoUs) with the Egyptian government for the establishment of green hydrogen plants, with corresponding amounts of US\$ 8 billion, US\$ 6 billion, and US\$ 4 billion. These companies are currently in the process of negotiating with the Egyptian government. Egyptian companies such as El-Sewedy Group (which manufactures smart electrometers), KAPCI Coatings (which manufactures automobile paints), Modern Waterproofing Group/Bitumode (which manufactures waterproofing membranes and protective boards for the building industry), and 700 Apps (which provides information technology services) have made investments in India totaling 37 million US dollars (Embassy of India, 2024).

Cultural Relations

Both its culture and its monuments are distinctively Egyptian. It is not Robert De Niro and Brad Pitt who are the most well-known international actors in Egypt; rather, it is Shah Rukh Khan and Amitabh Bachchan who receive the greatest attention. Considering this, the extent of the cultural tie and affinity is demonstrated. Tourism is a significant industry for both countries. It is unfortunate that up until this point, tourism between Egypt and India has been limited because there is only one direct flight between both countries, which departs from Mumbai and arrives in Cairo. When tourists from India visit Egypt, they are not only interested in visiting beaches and resorts; they are also particularly interested in visiting all the historical and cultural places that Egypt has to offer (Laskar, 2023). The number of people practicing yoga in Egypt has skyrocketed. The International Day of Yoga (IDY) was observed with great fervor in the year 2024. In the days leading up to the IDY celebrations that took place on June 21st, 2024 in Al-Horreya Park in Cairo, yoga activities were conducted in Alexandria, Hurghada, Luxor, Minya, and other cities. The competition known as “Yoga At Iconic Place” was organized by Mission, and Egyptians took part in it with significant enthusiasm. During the ceremonies of International Day of Yoga 2024, which took place in Srinagar, Jammu and Kashmir, on June 21, 2024, the Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi, brought attention to the increasing popularity of yoga in Egypt. In particular, he referred to the contest known as “Yoga At Iconic Places” and expressed his gratitude to young Egyptians for sharing yoga positions in well-known

tourist destinations such as the Pyramids, the Sphinx, and other such points of interest. During his Mann Ki Baat on June 30, 2024, the Prime Minister also referred to the growing popularity of yoga in Egypt and observed that a significant number of Egyptians were practicing yoga near the edge of the Nile River and the Red Sea (Embassy of India, 2024).

Cooperation in Higher Education

India and Egypt have announced a higher education cooperation plan to establish a joint institution, network universities, and increase student and academic mobility. Selected Egyptian and Indian universities will have Arabic and Indian studies chairs. Egyptian and Indian universities will also collaborate to create an Indian-style non-profit university. The proposal seeks to improve academic, scientific, and cultural cooperation between Indian and Egyptian universities and share teaching, research, and administrative best practices. The “Egyptian-Indian Dialogue for Higher Education for Sustainable Development” meeting in Beni Suef, Egypt, on 8-10 May 2017 produced the plan. Egypt’s Nahda University and central government enterprise and consultancy and project management organization EdCIL hosted the conference. A task force will identify priority areas for cooperation under the Indo-Egyptian plan, including modernizing curricula, reforming education to improve graduate employment and industry-university links, and plans to cope with the tremendous growth of knowledge. India’s EdCIL announced 10 grants for Nahda University in Beni Suef students to study for master’s and doctorate degrees in various scientific subjects at Indian universities at the conference. The Indian government offers Egyptian students’ scholarships. Hundreds of Egyptian students have received Indian Council for Cultural Relations Scholarships from top Indian universities. Samir Khalaf Abd-El-Aal, research professor at the National Research Centre in Cairo, said the Indo-Egyptian higher education cooperation plan was a “win-win deal” (Sawahel, 2017).

President Abdel Fatah al-Sisi opened the Global Forum for Higher Education and Scientific Research in Egypt’s New Administrative Capital with 2,000 high-ranking officials and famous figures. Bassam Radi, presidential spokesman said that President Sisi patronized the three-day forum, “Between the Present and the Future,” which brought together scientists, experts, and others interested in university education, scientific research, and innovation. According to local media, over 300 foreign figures attended, including prominent scientists, heads of

international universities, deputies' education ministers and education experts from 55 countries, and representatives of regional and international higher education and scientific research organizations. The forum seeks to offer an international platform for interaction and discussions on many global issues to address the present and future of higher education, scientific research, and innovation and share worldwide experiences (State Information Services, Egypt, 2019).

During his state visit to Egypt in 2022, India's Minister of External Affairs, S. Jaishankar, placed a strong emphasis on the need for higher education cooperation between India and Egypt. For the Indian Community in Egypt, he made a promise regarding the possibility of bilateral cooperation in higher education in a variety of disciplines. Since the arrival of the Modi government, India and Egypt have also worked together on many occasions regarding higher education (ANI, 2022).

Ayman Ashour Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research of Egypt, engaged in discussions with Ajit Gupta, the Indian Ambassador to Cairo, and his accompanying group regarding avenues for collaboration between Egypt and India in higher education and scientific research at the Ministry's headquarters. Ashour emphasized the significance of fostering scientific, research, and technological collaboration with India, commending the exceptional relations between Egypt and India, as well as their cooperation in higher education, particularly in technological education. He highlighted Egypt's commitment to advancing technological education and enhancing the qualifications of its graduates to meet market demands (State Information Service, 2022). The Distinguished Visitor's Programme of ICCR invited the Grand Mufti of Egypt, Dr. Shawky Ibrahim Allam, to discuss and promote education and cultural cooperation over six days. In addition to engagements in New Delhi, he visited Hyderabad, Agra, Aligarh, and Kozhikode over six days. On May 1, 2023, he met with Jamia Milia Islamia University Vice Chancellor Prof. Najma Akhtar during his official tour. He was welcomed by ICCR President Dr. Vinay Sahasrabuddhe, Director General Kumar Tuhin, and Secretary CPV, MEA Ausaf Sayeed, who discussed bilateral, cultural, and people-to-people ties. He spoke on "Dialogue Among Civilizations" at Aligarh Muslim University on 2 May 2023 and met Vice Chancellor Prof. Mohammad Gulrez. He stated, "There is a need to grasp and understand the true spirit of Islam that is engaging and dealing with people of all faiths, civilizations, and philosophies by seeking common grounds and recognizing the diversities

and differences which are a divine gift and blessing from God (ICCR, 2023)”. As a part of the India - Africa Maitri Scholarship Scheme, the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR), which is part of the Ministry of External Affairs, is offering thirteen spots to Egyptian students for the academic year 2024-2025. With the help of these slots, Egyptian students will have the opportunity to enroll in undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral programs at a wide range of Indian universities and instructional institutions (Press Releases, 2024).

Conclusion

Mahatma Gandhi and Saad Zaghloul shared common objectives in their nations' pursuit of independence, leading to a strong bond between leaders like Gamal Abdel Nasser and Jawaharlal Nehru. In 1955, India and Egypt signed a Friendship Treaty, and the establishment of the Maulana Azad Centre for Indian Culture (MACIC) in Cairo in 1992 to strengthen deeper cultural ties. Their partnership flourished within the Non-Aligned Movement, which they co-founded in 1955. After 2014 under Prime Minister Narendra Modi's leadership, India and Egypt have strengthened cooperation in political, economic, defense, and cultural spheres. Notable exchanges, including defense agreements and joint military exercises, have marked their growing strategic partnership, with both countries aligning on key global issues such as climate change and terrorism. The growing trade, investment, and cultural ties between India and Egypt reflect a strong and evolving bilateral relationship. Economic cooperation highlighted by India's increasing investments and trade volume, demonstrates mutual benefit and significant potential for growth. India's \$3.5 billion investment in Egypt, coupled with future agreements worth billions, indicates a promising economic future, especially in sectors like renewable energy, technology, and healthcare. The cultural exchange, particularly in areas like yoga and tourism, enhances people-to-people connections. Furthermore, the emphasis on higher education cooperation fosters academic collaboration, offering new opportunities for students and researchers. As both countries continue to strengthen these ties, their partnership promises to drive economic prosperity, educational development, and cultural exchange, creating a foundation for a long-term, mutually beneficial relationship. The focus on sectors like green hydrogen and technological education also positions both nations for continued growth and innovation in the years to come.

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